

NODES

Nord Ovest Digitale E Sostenibile

NODES – Nord Ovest Digitale e Sostenibile

FINAL REPORT ON PMFCs FOR ENVIRONMENTAL SENSORS AND VINEYARD HEALTH EVALUATION

SPOKE 6 – PRIMARY AGROINDUSTRY

FLAGSHIP PROJECT VINO

DELIVERABLE D3.3

Version history

No.	Date	Details	Author(s)
0.1	24 October 2025	Draft of document	Silvia Assini, Ilaria Brugellis, Nicholas Fiorani, Marco Grassi, Piero Malcovati, Federica Perego, Lorenzo Vigoni
0.2	22 November 2025	Draft version for internal review	Silvia Assini, Ilaria Brugellis, Nicholas Fiorani, Marco Grassi, Piero Malcovati, Federica Perego, Lorenzo Vigoni
1.0	26 November 2025	Final version of document	Silvia Assini, Ilaria Brugellis, Nicholas Fiorani, Marco Grassi, Piero Malcovati, Federica Perego, Lorenzo Vigoni

This document is part of the project NODES which has received funding from the MUR – Missione 4, Componente 2, Investimento 1.5 – Creazione e rafforzamento di “Ecosistemi dell’innovazione”, costruzione di “leader territoriali di R&S” – del PNRR funded by the European Union - NextGenerationEU with grant agreement no. ECS00000036

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Glossary

	Definition
Hub Coordinator (HC)	The Hub Coordinator represents the single point of contact for the implementation of the innovation ecosystem towards the MUR. It carries out the management and coordination activities of the innovation ecosystem, receives the fundings, verifies, and transmits to the MUR the reporting of the activities carried out by the Spoke and their affiliates.
National Recovery and Resilience Plan (NRRP)	This document uses the Italian acronym for the NRRP, which is PNRR (Piano Nazionale della Ripresa e Resilienza)
Research Program Manager	The person who will be responsible for the overall scientific contents of the NODES project. The NODES will appoint the Research Program Manager. It refers to "Responsabile del Programma di Ricerca" in the MUR's Call of proposal for "Ecosistemi di Innovazione"
NODES' Research and innovation program	NODES' Research and Innovation program is articulated in specific programs for each Spoke, with the aim to promote and support applied research on topics consistent with the Intelligent Specialization Strategy, with the guidelines of the 2021-2027 partnership agreement scheme, with regional operational plans and regional and national research and innovation priorities. Although NODES' Spokes are concentrated on different themes, they will organize their activities and actions within a common framework – NODES' Booster Methodology
Spoke Coordinator	The University in charge of coordinating the Spoke's ecosystem. It refers to "Spoke" in the MUR's Call of proposal for "Ecosistemi di Innovazione"
Spoke Data Manager	The person who will be responsible for the monitoring and management of data generated at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Data Manager.
Spoke Partner	The entity associated to the Spoke Coordinator. It can be an Innovation Cluster, Competence Center, Research Center related to the Spoke's ecosystem and contributes to achieve objectives and impact under the Spoke' leadership and management. It refers to "soggetti affiliati" in the MUR's Call of proposal for "Ecosistemi di Innovazione".
Spoke Project manager	The person who will be responsible for the management, coordination and progress of the project at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Project Manager.
Spoke research and innovation program	NODES' Research and Innovation program is articulated in specific programs for each Spokes. The spoke will leverage a consolidated collaboration with leading private and public companies and will focus the applied research activity on technological domains and applications that can favour the integration of SMEs into new value chains.
Spoke Scientific and Technical Manager	The person who will be responsible for the overall scientific contents of the project at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Scientific and Technical Manager.
Spoke Stakeholders Committee (SC)	Consultation structure formed by relevant stakeholders (Government, universities, companies, civil society, third sector, etc.)
Spoke Thematic	General target focus and domain of the Spoke research.
Spoke Topics	Specific areas/lines of development within the Spoke.
Spoke Work Package Leader	At the Spoke level, Work Packages (WPs) will be organized by WP leaders, who will be responsible for performance evaluation and reporting.
Flagship Project	Main research project at the Spoke level with the goal of prototyping, testing, and demonstrating the research activities towards higher TRLs.

In the context of the NODES project, a new indoor prototype of PMFC has been developed, with the pot (or jar) containing the plants being on the top and drainage water percolating to the container below, where a microbial fuel cell was placed. An ad hoc part of the prototype contains the electrical circuit realized by the engineering team, which also worked to optimize the energy harvesting procedure, as part of the project. This can be considered the demonstrator for the PMFC harvester complete prototype*.

Furthermore, other activities carried out during the project include:

- Optimization of the electrical performance of PMFCs in indoor environment.
- Experimentation in outdoor environment.
- Development and characterization of DC-DC electronics for PMFC energy harvesting
- Measure of actual continuous power available (bacteria's instant continuous power)
- Development of a smart JAR prototype for PMFC+energy harvesting electronics*

The project was implemented over three years.

The main activities and outputs realized in the project about PMFC research and characterization are described below, in chronological order. Details will be given instead about the development of the actual prototype (smart Jar), including PMFC and detailed measurements, as well as energy harvesting electronics in a separated paragraph, being a continuous activity throughout the three years. Same applies for measurements about peak and actual available continuous power from PMFCs, i.e. bacteria's instant and continuous power.

Project Timeline Breakdown

First Year

Bibliographic study - The preliminary analysis of PMFC literature highlighted nomenclature issues causing doubts about the interpretation of the right species used in the PMFC experimentation, making it difficult to trace back to the species that were actually tested. Preliminary results also seemed to highlight that electrical performances were affected both by “Raunkiær life forms” and “Root system type”. Furthermore, these results seemed to suffer from limitations due to the lack of a common benchmark for electrical measures, implying a necessary approximation of power density values.

Second Year

Bibliographic study/Review production - The nomenclatural issues identified in the previous bibliographic study, along with the results obtained from the analysis of the plant traits “Raunkiær life forms” and “Root system type”, were refined. Then, a synthesis was implemented in an organized manner, leading to the production of a review paper. This paper (Brugellis et al., 2024) was published in the multidisciplinary international journal Heliyon (Cell Press, IF: 3.4, CS: 4.5), receiving a fair amount of praise from the reviewers (<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2024.e38733>).

Indoor experimentation – It was articulated in two sub-activities.

1) Complete long-term experimentation to understand which carbon pellet internal layering was the best (“Double layer” on anode and cathode or “Single layer” on cathode) in MFCs. Although a statistically significant result was obtained only for the voltage, all other parameters showed more stable values around the median of the distributions in the 'Single layer' set. This can be considered a positive outcome, in fact this is also cost-effective for the construction of cells, which will result in a little more convenient and easier to build.

2) Starting of long-term experimentation with urea treatment of the *Spathiphyllum lanceifolium* (Jacq.) Schott plants feeding both “Double layer” and “Single layer” of carbon pellet MFCs. The experimentation with urea did not yield the desired results. In cases of statistical significance (current and power), the “Control” cells showed higher values. In the “Single layer” set, the treated cells had more stable distributions for the same parameters, but with very low values.

Outdoor experimentation - It was articulated in two sub-activities.

1) Testing different plant species with different plant traits, to understand their possible effect on electrical performance. A preliminary analysis of data collected in the second year was carried out. For all measured parameters (see the next point Data collection), with exception of voltage, significant results were obtained from the statistical tests. *Allium angulosum* L. emerged as the

most suitable species among the three chosen (*Allium angulosum* L., *Carex remota* L., *Lythrum salicaria* L.) for the experimentation.

2) Testing of MFCs made with gold cathode at the cable end. In general, the median values of the parameter distributions appear to be higher, but also more dispersed, and in any case, the differences were not significant for this preliminary analysis.

Data collection/Statistical analysis - Measurements of voltage (mV peak) current (mA peak), and current after 5 seconds (mA at 5s) were collected weekly for both the outdoor and the indoor experimental setups. Power (mW) was indirectly calculated. Table 1 reported the number of measurements realized in the second year for both indoor and outdoor experimentations. Statistical analyses were evaluated on a case-by-case basis for each experimental design.

Table 1. Summary of data collection activity during the second year.

	Activity	N° of collected measurement (mV and mA)	Period
Indoor	Carbon pellet layering	2598 x 3	28/02/2023 16/02/2024
	Urea treatment	1266 x 3	27/02/2024 05/09/2024
Outdoor	Plant species and golden cathode	864 x 3	14/05/2024 17/09/2024

Implementation of environmental sensing

Third Year

The main activities realized in the third year are described as follows.

Paper preparation and submission about indoor experimentation of carbon pellets layering and urea treatment - Previous results have been refined and synthesized in an organized manner, leading to the production of a manuscript, titled "Evaluating a new prototype of Plant Microbial Fuel Cell: is the electrical performance affected by carbon pellet layering and urea treatment?", which has been published in the international journal "Energies" (IF: 3.2; CS: 7.3). (<https://doi.org/10.3390/en18195320>).

Indoor experimentation - It was articulated in two sub-activities.

1) Experimentation to understand which internal configuration was best, with or without membrane. The control set with membrane shows consistently higher values than the control set with soil only (without membrane).

2) Experimentation with *Trichoderma* treatment, either applied to *Spathiphyllum lanceifolium* plants feeding the cells or directly to the cells themselves, in both membrane and non-

membrane MFCs. Significant differences were found between the distributions of voltage and current values, with positive values for the sets treated with *Trichoderma* in both membrane and non-membrane cells.

Completing the outdoor experimentation

1) Testing different plant species with different plant traits. Data collected during the second and part of the third year were analysed. The results confirm what emerged during the preliminary analysis realized in the second year. For all parameters, except voltage, significant results were obtained from the statistical tests. *Allium angulosum* emerged as the most suitable species among the three chosen for the experimentation. This is fairly consistent with the observations made regarding the results of the literature review. *A. angulosum* is a bulbous geophyte and thus included in the 'Taproot' root type group, which in Brugellis et al. (2024) shows values comparable to those of adventitious plants.

2) Testing performance among cells with gold against classical copper cathode cables. For all parameters, except current after 5 seconds, significant results were obtained from the statistical tests. In general, the median values of the parameter distributions appear to be higher, but also more dispersed for the gold cathode configuration. This can be considered a positive outcome, with practical implications for future experiments.

Data collection/Statistical analysis - Measurements of voltage (mV peak) current (mA peak), and current after 5 seconds (mA at 5s) were collected weekly for both the outdoor and the indoor experimental setups. Power (mW) was indirectly calculated. Table 2 reported the number of measurements realized in the second year for both indoor and outdoor experiments. Statistical analyses were evaluated on a case-by-case basis for each experimental design.

Table 2. Summary of data collection activity in the third year.

	Activity	N° of collected measurement (mV and mA)	Period
Indoor	Membrane and <i>Trichoderma</i> treatment	1656 x 3	20/11/2024 24/04/2025
Outdoor	Plant species and golden cathode	1981 x 3	14/05/2024 12/05/2025

PMFC Energy Harvesting

Energy harvesting is the practice of extracting electrical energy from the surrounding environment, allowing us to power a load without the need for batteries or external power lines. In our case, we used Plant Microbial Fuel Cells (PMFCs) to extract this electrical energy from the environment. In this paragraph we'll illustrate how this happens and how the process has been optimized. Microbial Fuel Cells (MFCs) essentially transform the chemical energy produced by microbial metabolism and oxidation-reduction processes into electrical energy that can be used for various purposes (Figure. 1).

Figure 1 – PMFC electro-chemical process schematic

Specifically, Plant Microbial Fuel Cells (PMFCs) harness a plant's excess organic matter, deposited near its roots (rhizodeposition). Through photosynthesis, plants convert solar radiation into biochemical energy in the form of sugars. A small portion of these carbohydrates is used by the plant itself, while the remainder is released into the soil, along with other organic matter, in the form of root exudates. Microorganisms are essentially supplied by the plant itself. In fact, microorganisms and active bacteria present in the soil are able to degrade organic matter, thus producing positive Hydrogen ions and electrons through microbial metabolism (redox reactions). The energy yield of this type of system depends on multiple factors: the anode and cathode construction materials (according to A. Volta principle/effect), the type of plant, and the lighting conditions in the area where the plant is located. Different construction techniques could affect the results, but to date of project kick-off, no studies have clearly demonstrated substantial differences in the yield of cells with the same operating principle but constructed using different techniques. This technology has been tested with both soil-rooted plants and aquatic plants (Figure 2).

Figure 2 – Schematic diagram for PMFC implementation

If a higher voltage is required, it would obviously be possible to use multiple cells connected together, creating a PMFC chain (Figure 3). We'll see later if the best solution is in series, in parallel or other.

Figure 3 – Array of PMFCs to augment available power

The Developed PMFC

In this latter type of cell, the system is fed by wastewater from watering potted plants. In this way, the wastewater, rich in nutrient exudates from plant roots, feeds the bacterial communities present in the cells. This method of separating plant and cell is highly practical for maintenance of processes, as it is possible to repair or replace the eventual damaged part without necessarily having to remove the plant. For example, very frequent actions are required to replace the cathode, which is damaged due to the oxidation reaction that occurs in the cell.

A recent innovation (discovered within this project) that has significantly improved the performance of PMFC cells has been to keep the percolated water in contact with the roots for a longer period of time than it would take to just travel through the soil.

To do this, it was simply necessary to provide a saucer that would collect this water and keep it in contact with the root system before allowing it to flow into the compartment below containing the PMFC (Figure 4).

Figure 4 – PMFC including raw example of empowering saucer solution

This is currently still a prototype, but the enormous potential of this improvement was immediately recognized. The inclusion of the saucer has allowed, in addition to a significant increase in performance, also improved the health of the plant, which is able to absorb liquids for a longer period of time, limiting the risk of dehydration. The prototype was developed at the Flora, Vegetation, and Ecosystem Laboratory of University of Pavia (Department of Earth and Environmental Sciences). For raw measurements, the cells are placed in a basin and fed by water percolated from potted plants (Figure 5).

Figure 5 – Examples of 4 PMFCs with plant roots-leachate water

We will illustrate the cell structure, evaluating the characteristics and challenges that distinguish each individual component. A plastic box for electric plants was used to create the cells, protecting and keeping the contents compact minimizing material leakage over slots, mandatory for water interaction.

A woven-non-woven fabric (polypropylene microfibers) separator membrane (placed between the soil and the cathode) allows air to pass through while remaining impermeable. This membrane also provides a surface on which the bacterial community can proliferate. Initial sugars are also placed near the membrane, which encourage growth. The upper layer contains 3mm carbon pellets, which limit emissions from the decomposition of organic material and also reduce odors. The cells we used were constructed using two techniques: single- and double-layer pellets. Carbon felt is stapled to a copper wire to construct the cathode. This material was chosen because the cathode is exposed to oxygen, which causes oxidation. Carbon felt resists oxidation better than other conductive materials. This material, although much more expensive, is essential for the construction of the cathode, which would otherwise need to be replaced much more frequently. Oxidation remains a problem; very often, the damaged wire is simply replaced, leaving the carbon felt untouched. To address this issue, new materials are being evaluated to plate the wire and the cathode attachment, which can delay oxidation. Cable replacement seems much easier, given the cell's structure, but it is still under optimization. Located at the base of the cell, the cathode is composed of an aluminum foil onto which a stripped copper wire is soldered. Unlike the cathode, oxidation cannot occur in the anode compartment because, under proper maintenance, it is submerged in water and therefore oxygen-free. In the event of mechanical failure, replacement is more invasive due to the difficulty of repair. In fact, if it is necessary to replace it, the process is very laborious, essentially requiring the cell to be disassembled and reassembled. Regarding the bacterial component, certain bacterial families were initially inoculated into the soil and the cell to allow for faster proliferation. To date, this method has been deemed useless, as the stochastic component present in this biological process far outweighs

the benefits provided by inoculating these bacteria. Therefore, currently, the bacteria naturally present in the soil and in the organic substrate used to build the cell are used. No deterioration or improvement in the process has been observed, so it can be stated that working with the bacteria naturally present in the soil rather than inoculating them does not alter the performance of the cells in any way. To better nourish the bacterial community, the use of urea (carbonic acid diamide), which dissolves very easily in water, is being studied. Specifically, it is used at a concentration of 3 g/l and is supplied to the PMFCs through normal plant watering, placing the plants above the basin containing the cells (Figure 6). No effective improved results were obtained.

Figure 6 – Real plant upon PMFC cell prototype

Choice of The Plant

The choice of the plant is also vital to ensuring the cells function properly. To select the best candidate, we first consider the plant's energy performance, which it can achieve. The following table presents an extract from an experimental study of varying duration on various plant species (Table 3).

Table 3 – Results from Plant Microbial Fuel Cell by M. Azizul Moqsud (30 days observation)

Name of plant species	Duration of operation	Highest Power Density (PD) recorded and reported
<i>Canna indica</i>	140 Days	18 mW/m ²

Name of plant species	Duration of operation	Highest Power Density (PD) recorded and reported
<i>Physcomitrella patens</i>	70 Days	6.7 ± 0.6 mW/m ²
<i>Lolium perenne</i>	70 Days	55 mA/m ²
<i>Sporobolus arabicus</i>	60 Days	120 mW/m ²
<i>Typha latifolia</i>	228 Days	93 mW/m ³
<i>Phragmites australis</i>	160 Days	22 mW/m ²
<i>Spartina anglica</i>	160 Days	82 mW/m ²
<i>Brassica juncea</i>	30 Days	69.32 mW/m ²
<i>Trigonella foenumgraecum</i>	30 Days	80.26 mW/m ²
<i>Canna 'Stuttgart'</i>	30 Days	222.54 mW/m ²
<i>Sedum sexangulare</i>	360 Days	0.0084 μW/m ²
<i>Sedum rupestre</i>	360 Days	0.0155 μW/m ²
<i>Sedum hybridum</i>	360 Days	0.092 μW/m ²
<i>Acorus tatarinowii</i>	51 Days	21 mW/m ²
<i>Puccinellia distans</i>	114 Days	83.7 mW/m ²
<i>Chlorophytum comosum</i>	100 Days	18 mW/m ²
<i>Epipremnum aureum</i>	60 Days	15.38 mW/m ²
<i>Dracaena braunii</i>	60 Days	12.78 mW/m ²
<i>Chasmanthe floribunda</i>	100 Days	0.21 mW/m ²
<i>Papyrus cyperus</i>	100 Days	1.083 mW/m ²
<i>Chlorophytum comosum</i>	100 Days	18 mW/m ²
<i>Spartina anglica</i>	105 Days	1.04 mW/m ²

This investigation of energy density is important for choosing the right plant, but it ignores other characteristics that influence the choice. The characteristics that the plant should have, to be considered functional for our purposes, are ease of cultivation, the ability to maintain its health in low light, and tolerance and frequent watering, to maintain adequate water and nutrient levels

to support the bacterial communities at the anode. These characteristics led us to select *Spathiphyllum lanceifolium* as the plant suitable for our purpose (Figure 7).

Figure 7- *Spathiphyllum lanceifolium*

The choice proved optimal due to its highly developed root system, combined with a foliage system that allows the plant to survive even in low light. This means that under the same external conditions, this plant produces greater free radicals, thanks to the work of the bacteria present in the PMFC. *Spathiphyllum lanceifolium* is, in fact, a plant that naturally grows in the undergrowth, in low-light conditions, and therefore adapts very well to the laboratory (it is, in fact, sold as an indoor ornamental plant). Furthermore, it is a hygrophilous plant, meaning it is suited to humid environments, can be watered frequently, and is not particularly affected by waterlogging. It therefore allows us to have the right quantities of a leachate, rich in organic material, to use in the cell (the anode compartment of the cells must always remain submerged, therefore it requires a lot of water). Beyond the purely technical aspects, it is an evergreen plant with glossy, shiny leaves, easy to maintain and easy to flower. It therefore also has ornamental value, which is well suited to the prospect of using technology in urban and domestic settings.

The above considerations were made based on our case, and therefore, with different plant types. A different plant may be chosen, depending on the required characteristics. We are aware of the fact that vineyard is cultivated on a dryer soil. However, we must consider that PMFC performance is proportional to water density and bacteria proliferation near the roots, which depends also on plant's health. Considering this, we are carrying out studies (either indoors and outdoors) about correlation between power production and plants health. To have a more complete scenario we need also temperature and humidity measure of the environment (for this reason we'll supply a battery-less Bluetooth low energy digital thermometer and a hygrometer as harvester's load). So

far, within the project we have not ended up to a final consideration about correlation between vineyard health and PMFC power, especially because of derating of power due to dryer lands of vineyards, which leads to a lower data loudness (i.e. significance in a statistical dataset). However, we are verifying whether produced power and positive health conditions of plants are proportional.

Preliminary Measurements on PMFC

A preliminary data collection on PMFCs has been carried out in the Flora, Vegetation, and Ecosystem Services Laboratory at the Department of Earth and Environmental Sciences of University of Pavia. This data was collected on a sample of 47 PMFCs built using two construction methods: single- and double-layer carbon pellets. Three different measurements were performed: two current measurements (expressed in mA) and one voltage measurement (expressed in mV): specifically, peak current, five-second after current, and maximum voltage. The values found were often fluctuating, but in any case, it was easy to determine when the desired peaks for measurement were reached. To perform the desired measurements, a benchtop multimeter was used (even if a hand-held digital multimeter is adequate and also seldom used), connected to the cell with two different configurations, depending on the type of measurement being performed. The multimeters acted as a voltmeter for voltage measurement and as an ammeter. The configurations, however, differed depending on their use: when used as a voltmeter, it was connected in parallel to the cell, while when used as an ammeter, the connection was in series. One of the main objectives of the research, associated with the collection of these electrical measurements, is to experimentally determine a method that can predict cell performance. Cell performance may refer, for instance, to the length of time during which the PMFC's voltage and current remain optimal, but of course it depends on the power drawn. Not all PMFCs are able to produce the right amount of energy required for our purposes. The values thus collected, for each cell, were then entered into a database measures file for various types of statistical evaluations. In addition to the measured values, the tables also show an identification code (ID) for each PMFC and the power obtained (not measured) as a function of the measured voltage and current, like in Table 4. In certain PMFCs, where values of at least one of these physical quantities were found to be too low, it was necessary to discard the cell and recycle its components to build a new one.

Table 4 – Weekly measurements on PMFC from 07/02/2024 to 25/07/2024

ID	V [mV]	I peak [mA]	I 5s [mA]	P* [μW]
DSP6	562	0,024	0,016	13,488
DSP6	644	0,023	0,023	14,812
DSP6	560	0,027	0,025	15,12
DSP6	487	0,069	0,057	33,603
DSP6	552	0,033	0,033	18,216
DSP6	365	0,032	0,024	11,68
DSP6	680	0,4	0,386	272
DSP6	555	0,306	0,22	169,83
DSP6	460	0,278	0,26	127,88
DSP6	561	0,54	0,496	302,94
DSP6	505	0,163	0,149	82,315
DSP6	495	6,45	3,418	3192,75
DSP6	500	0,463	0,449	231,5
DSP6	462	3,314	0,262	1531,068
DSP6	393	1,078	0,908	423,654
DSP6	600	2,732	2,683	1639,2
DSP6	380	1,49	1,404	566,2
DSP6	327	2,93	0,013	0,009
DSP6	330	0,021	0,017	0,009
DSP6	269	0,022	0,018	0,009

It is useful to note that the period of these measurements (which are weekly) runs from February 7, 2024, to July 25, 2024. The cell IDs are not intended to provide information but are simply codes to characterize the PMFC in the laboratory. This evaluation is not guaranteed to maintain overtime, but it is a good starting value, so that the cell can perform well for a longer period of time. Different conclusions were reached about the current. We are interested in the peak initial short-circuit current (and in current after 5 seconds) but most important data would be to find the value of the actual bacteria's current (a specific paragraph is dedicated to such research), i.e. the maximum amount of current theoretically available for an indefinite period of time, without exploiting accumulation of charges in soil or artificial tanks. The minimum I_{short} current that proved to be a sign of the cell's validity and reliability over time was 700-800 mA. Obviously, higher values would be better, but this is the minimum we accept for evaluating a PMFC suitable for use as a power supply in our circuits.

Table 5 – Preliminary measurements on peak PMFCs short circuit current, in mA (cells will be further optimized during the project)

CRDSP1	CRDSP2	CRDSP3	CRDSP4	DSP1	DSP2	PSSC1	PSSC2	PSSC3
0,124	0,339	0,005	0,012	0,96	0,418	0,012	0,036	0,01
0,196	0,202	0,002	1,94	1,335	0,074	0,022	0,042	0,005
0,309	0,101	0,005	0,619	2,839	0,09	0,012	0,062	0,004
0,108	0,072	0,003	0,721	1,036	0,067	0	0,038	0,011
0,121	0,38	0,005	0,525	0,25	0	0	0,032	0,009
0,141	0,068	0,005	0,663	0,45	0,024	0,038	0,032	0,009
0,003	0,068	0,01	0,06	0,024	0,02	0,026	0,036	0,009
0,188	0,119	0,003	0,068	4,402	0,027	0,024	0,036	0,006
0,063	0,058	0,011	0,009	0,135	0,008	0,02	0,023	0,008
0,188	0,022	0,015	0,126	0,052	0,024	0,017	0,05	0,008
0,025	0,034	0,003	0,002	2,815	0,028	0,018	0,028	0,006
5,551	0,036	0,007	2,002	0,09	0,047	0,168	0,28	0,006
3,72	0,046	0,009	0,93	0,105	0,03	0,145	0,026	0,007
2,536	0,053	0,004	0,864	0,226	0,013	0,28	0,002	0,006
2,36	0,034	0,036	3,64	0,068	0,019	0,163	0,015	0,008
2,703	0,412	0,015	0,431	0,021	0,09	0,297	0,024	0,009
2,75	0,125	0,005	0,508	0,137	0	0,071	0	0,008
0,632	0,148	0,028	0,247	0,093	0,012	0,131	0	0,006
0,277	0,097	0,005	0,02	0,045	0,009	0,102	0,04	0,008
1,351	0,001	0,034	0,031	0	0,011	0,183	0,002	0,008
0,011	0,171	0,004	0,024	0,053	0,022	0,092	0,037	0,008
0,002	0,099	0,019	0,003	0,032	0,012	0,035	0,021	0,001
0,001	0,064	0,006	0,003	0,036	0,001	0	0,018	0,003
0,002	0,041	0,013	0,001	0,031	0,01	0,221	0,025	0,001

Regarding the current value 5 seconds after the peak (Table 6) it is used to verify that the cell can maintain a reasonable value of current for a few seconds, without decreasing excessively. Here too, to evaluate which parameter value could provide a positive prediction regarding the cell's performance, we preferred to work first with the initial open circuit voltage. In a second time, we evaluated the time it takes for the short circuit current to halve. The longer this time, the better the PMFC will perform.

Table 6 – Short circuit current value (in mA) after 5 seconds

CRDSP1	CRDSP2	CRDSP3	CRDSP4	DSP1	DSP2	PSSC1	PSSC2	PSSC3
0,089	0,218	0,004	0,006	0,384	0,349	0	0,01	0,002
0,107	0,196	0,002	1,937	0,246	0,063	0,01	0,028	0,006
0,213	0,076	0,003	0,445	2,512	0,076	0,006	0,05	0,002
0,081	0,068	0,003	0,492	0,992	0,063	0	0,017	0,011
0,093	0,336	0,003	0,368	0,183	0	0	0,021	0,007
0,095	0,063	0,004	0,461	0,356	0,021	0,006	0,017	0,009
0,003	0,055	0,009	0,051	0	0,018	0,021	0,019	0,009
0,162	0,071	0,003	0,054	2,701	0,025	0,021	0,027	0,006
0,058	0,056	0,01	0,007	0,128	0,002	0,019	0,014	0,006

0,152	0,022	0,014	0,093	0,041	0,023	0,014	0,037	0,008
0,012	0,028	0,002	0,001	0,73	0,024	0,015	0,012	0,005
4,62	0,014	0,007	1,889	0,079	0,046	0,144	0,22	0,006
3,478	0,044	0,004	0,615	0,049	0,029	0,093	0,023	0,006
2,384	0,044	0,003	0,581	0,186	0,013	0,158	0,002	0,006
2,318	0,026	0,006	3,618	0,025	0,018	0,117	0,013	0,007
2,604	0,398	0,011	0,421	0,011	0,083	0,273	0,019	0,008
2,576	0,088	0,004	0,463	0,117	0	0,068	0	0,007
0,603	0,139	0,024	0,219	0,086	0,01	0,107	0	0,005
0,273	0	0,005	0,013	0,039	0,004	0,086	0,026	0,007
1,328	0,001	0,029	0,029	0	0,009	0,154	0,001	0,006
0,011	0,14	0,003	0,009	0,038	0,021	0,067	0,031	0,005
0,002	0,083	0,013	0,002	0,028	0,01	0,034	0,018	0,001
0,001	0,056	0,004	0,001	0,034	0	0	0,018	0,003
0,001	0,038	0,008	0,001	0,023	0,008	0,178	0,022	0,001

A common acceptable halving time for short circuit current has been experimentally determined to be around 8 seconds.

The Power Figure of Merit for PMFCs

A wattmeter has not been used to measure power, since it is derived rather than measured, to be a sort of theoretical prediction of how much power we could obtain under ideal conditions. We still call it power, because it has the same unit of measurement, although, in fact, it would be more correct to define it as a Figure of Merit (FoM) of the cell (Table 7). The power thus defined is obtainable when the voltage is equal to half of open circuit voltage (f_{em}) value and when the current is equal to half the initial short circuit value (I_{short}), thus obtaining the figure of merit cited above. $FoM [in W] = f_{em} \cdot I_{short} / 4$. It is important to note that the f_{em} (electromotive force or open circuit voltage) and the I_{short} initial current correspond to the maximum voltage and current that can be reached in the circuit without employing DC-DC converters. The power actually produced by the chemical reaction in the PMFC, if used continuously, would be too low and approximately reduced by a factor of 1/10 or even 1/20 compared to the previously defined figure of merit. This will be one of the main reasons for using a supercapacitor in the DC-DC converter for energy harvesting rather than directly using the cell as a power supply (this topic will be discussed in the following chapters). We remind that also the cell itself is an accumulator. In fact, if the PMFC is not used for a significant time, the performance regarding instant power will increase due to augmented availability free charge elements concentration in wet soil. First, a statistical analysis was conducted based on the data collected to assess whether double-layer pallets offer greater advantages than single-layer pallets. To do this, the averages for each cell and the averages of the averages for each type of measurement performed were calculated.

Table 7 – Measured power figure of merit for PMFCs, in μW for different types of PMFCs

CRDSP1	CRDSP2	CRDSP3	CRDSP4	DSP1	DSP2	PSSC1	PSSC2	PSSC3
43,896	151,872	2,46	2,4	556,8	238,26	6,432	16,236	5,37
115,836	111,908	1,044	1701,38	863,745	42,402	13,42	22,428	2,74
153,573	54,439	2,595	472,297	1839,672	46,08	7,104	33,728	2,524
44,064	37,728	1,515	524,167	536,648	35,376	0	20,254	7,128
50,941	203,68	2,545	292,425	130	0	0	12,8	5,868
70,5	36,924	2,53	323,544	261,45	12,408	24,738	17,824	5,868
1,467	29,988	4,68	51,18	12,24	9,2	15,6	16,128	5,175
69,56	58,905	1,299	34,68	2205,402	10,395	14,4	19,044	3,432
23,31	28,304	4,873	3,798	64,53	3,792	13,8	9,108	5,44
74,072	9,02	6,045	41,958	24,856	10,656	10,353	35,85	5,28
6,65	16,728	1,281	0,812	1477,875	12,656	9	10,192	3,762
3669,211	11,664	2,87	1655,654	54	19,74	84,504	105,84	3,054
2630,04	21,896	3,906	669,6	32,655	13,5	58,29	11,96	3,85
1577,392	23,903	1,648	561,6	91,304	5,98	206,64	1,072	3,792
1611,88	15,232	14,148	2209,48	28,56	8,17	132,519	6,15	5,192
1724,514	170,568	5,925	171,969	7,056	36,09	175,824	10,968	5,832
1820,5	57	2,08	260,096	53,567	0	27,264	0	5,432
302,728	72,076	12,432	104,728	38,316	5,508	81,22	0	3,948
121,326	44,62	2,16	5	16,11	3,618	67,524	16,96	4,672
595,791	0,506	15,402	12,307	0	4,708	122,793	1,002	4,808
4,147	64,125	1,696	9,6	23,85	9,46	47,288	16,872	4,96
0,418	41,481	7,372	0,387	12,64	5,076	14,735	11,466	0,648
0,207	29,184	2,568	0,855	16,956	0,446	0	11,79	2,172
0,436	18,532	5,837	0,13	14,663	3,84	33,813	12,7	0,612

Starting from these values, Past 4.09 software was used to statistically assess whether there was a clear dependence on the construction method. The result was "no evidence for either equal or unequal means," meaning there was no evidence that one was better than the other. This could be due to the limited time period (only six months) in which the study was conducted. This result should not be interpreted as negative; it should simply be considered that, at present, there is no construction technique that improves the measurement results. Future research better defined, thanks to the collection of more data. However, an empirical rule, derived experimentally, has been found to predict the lifespan of a cell that, over the period considered, performed at acceptable levels. For main parameters measured values.

Peak Voltage (fem) 700-800 mV

I_{short} 750 - 800 mA

Halving-life with respect to fem 7-8 s

This rule does not guarantee that all cells within the required statistics will maintain good performance over time, but it is a very valid test for selecting a subset of PMFCs that are likely to

last much longer than others when connected to a load. Tests have thus shown better cell performance over time, allowing us to use the same cell to power our load for months. Obviously, this power supply was not continuous, as this would likely have damaged or temporarily made inefficient the PMFC.

The Developed Boost DC-DC Converter for Energy Harvesting

The PMFC is not used directly to power the load, because bacterial operation alone would not produce enough voltage to meet the load's nominal demands. We can augment the voltage paying in terms of reduced average available current by using a DC-DC boost converter. Furthermore, if you kept the PMFC constantly connected, you risk damaging it and quickly exhausting it without being able to provide the necessary energy. The controller circuit used was the Texas Instruments bq25504 (Figure 8), an ultra-low power boost converter able to work with very low initial input voltage values and thus suitable for energy harvesting. It was the first of a new family of intelligent integrated solutions for nano-power management for energy harvesting, ideal for meeting the unique needs of ultra-low-power applications.

Figure 8 – bq25504 energy harvester DC-DC boost manager by Texas Instrument (TI)

The product is specifically designed to efficiently capture and manage power in the microWatt to milliWatt range, generated by a variety of DC sources, such as thermoelectric generators or photovoltaics or, in our case, PMFCs. The bq25504 is the first device of its kind to implement a high-efficiency boost converter/charger aimed at products and systems, such as wireless sensor networks (WSNs), that have stringent operational and power requirements. The bq25504 design begins with a DC-DC boost converter/charger that requires only a few microwatts of power to begin operation. It is important to note that DC-DC converters are circuits that, receiving a direct voltage as input, present an output voltage that is still direct (in reality an average value) but of a different value than the input. To protect the battery (actually a charge storage super-capacitor in our case) from overvoltage, once the voltage reaches the V_{BAT_OV} (Over Voltage) threshold, the boost converter is disabled. To protect against under voltage, the system load should be disabled or reduced if the battery voltage approaches the V_{BAT_LUV} (Under Voltage) threshold. Schematic of developed DC-DC boost converter is shown in Figure 9.

Figure 9 – Schematic of developed DC-DC boost converter based on TI bq25504

It is therefore advisable to set the V_{BAT_OK} threshold above the V_{BAT_UV} threshold to ensure safe system operation. V_{BAT_OK} is the voltage value at which the energy is considered enough (with some margin) to supply the load by connecting it. At the input of the boost IC, there is a switch, a component that controls the start-up and operation of the boost converter, while at the output there is another switch which connects the load. The additional input switch is responsible for limiting the energy stored in an inductor during the switching cycle. We remind in fact that a DC-DC boost circuit consists of two main switches (which are internal in the TI chip in our case study) and an inductor as well as a load capacitor, which has not to be confused with the battery-like storage element of the system. This input switch (which is in addition to the main internal switches of the boost) can be made with transistors or other components. In our case we have a JFET P type outside the chip, which serves to connect and disconnect the cell when necessary. The choice of using a JFET may seem unusual but it was preferred to a more modern enhancement P-MOS because, even if they feature the same basic functionality, P-MOS device needs an overdrive voltage to conduct on its control terminals (over its threshold) which is not present when the system is at startup time, without available energy to have such voltage drop. P type JFET operates like a natural MOS and it is conductive without any voltage drop at its control terminals. Finally, P type has been used instead of N type because the device must turn off when the voltage at its gate augments. This solid-state switch is controlled directly by one of the pins

(Figure 10) of the Texas Instruments controller called V_{BAT_OK} , which also controls, with opposite polarity the load connector switch (actually a N-MOS this time).

Figure 10 – Schematic of developed circuit to connect and disconnect PMFC generator from the DC-DC boost input

This pin indicates when the supercapacitor has reached sufficient charge to power a load. Furthermore, when the supercapacitor is ready to discharge, the gate of the N-MOS is also powered, which controls the activation of the load. Furthermore, since N-MOS devices pass better low voltage rather than high voltages as a switch we disconnect and re-connect the ground from the load instead of the supply. If we try to pass high voltages with an N-MOS conducting, we would lose a voltage equal to the transistor's threshold voltage. Conversely, if I used P-MOS and low voltages, I would obtain the same loss, in modulus. The N-MOS has been successfully used to connect and disconnect the load (sensor and/or pulsed light system). It's useful to note that the JFET (cell) and the N-MOS (load) are in antiphase; that is, when the JFET allows the cell to supply energy to the supercapacitor, the MOSFET is closed. Conversely, when the MOSFET closes, supplying energy from the supercapacitor to the load, the JFET opens, disconnecting the PMFC. This behavior leads to its informal name: load and cell connection and disconnection. Using the two actions in antiphase is particularly useful for the PMFC, since, being disconnected from the rest of the circuit, it can begin to recharge, while the supercapacitor empties, powering the load. If this did not happen, the cell would run out of power much faster, significantly shortening the bacterial life cycle inside it, requiring more frequent maintenance or even replacement. The developed and fabricated DC-DC boost is reported in Figure 11 (Patented sub-sections darkened)

Figure 11 – Developed and fabricated DC-DC boost converter for PMFC energy harvesting

Extending the Generator: PMFCs in parallel

If greater power is required, multiple PMFCs may need to be connected together to meet the load's needs. A first approach might be to connect them in series, managing each cell as if it were a photovoltaic module, obtaining a total voltage that would be the sum of the voltages across all the individual modules. However, such a connection would be inconvenient, since despite a significant increase in voltage, a failure of one cell would interrupt the system's operation. In this way, the overall system's performance would be too dependent on any faults, risking a lack of current at the terminals due to a single faulty cell. The choice therefore fell on a parallel connection between the PMFCs, with a safety diode for each branch at the connection to prevent potential damage from currents of broken cells. The only precaution to take into account is to make the connection downstream of the DC-DC boost to avoid losing too much percentage of voltage because of the diode's threshold voltage. It is therefore necessary for each PMFC to be equipped with its own converter circuit (expensive), and the connections should be made only downstream of it. Given the modest voltages, we have to use a Schottky diode to lose a threshold voltage almost half that of a normal diode.

Environmental measurements

The entire process described above is used to power an IoT (Internet of Things) sensor, connected in parallel with a flashlight, which we will discuss later. The purpose of this sensor is to measure temperature and humidity in a closed or open environment. The sensor used is the SHT4.1 from SENSIRION (Figure 12).

Figure 12 – Sensirion SHT 4 family temperature and humidity sensor

This gadget allows you to read real-time values on a screen or send the collected data via Bluetooth low energy to a mobile or desktop device. It is also possible to view statistics on the measurements taken using the MyAmbience app always by third party SENSIRION (Figure 13).

Figure 13 – Sensirion My Ambience App GUI

To use even less energy, it would be possible to turn off the screen and use only Bluetooth as an output, increasing the device's operating time before exhausting the energy supplied by the supercapacitor. Measurements are given in degrees Celsius (°C or °F) for temperature and as a percentage of relative humidity (%RH). Relative humidity measures water vapor relative to air temperature; that is, it measures the actual amount of water vapor in the air compared to the total amount of vapor the air could contain without natural dew generation at that temperature. The sensor was designed to measure ambient temperatures in common environments, so it performs best for temperatures measured in the range from 0°C to 60°C. The sensor's operation is not continuous but depends on the charge-discharge times of the capacitor in the circuit upstream of the load. The better the cell's condition, the shorter the battery charging time, reducing the data loss period. The lower the load's energy consumption, the longer the supercapacitor will discharge, allowing for a greater number of measured data. By combining a

longer discharge time with a shorter charging time, we can obtain a list of measurements, which, while not continuous, is large enough to evaluate the average temperatures and humidity in a given environment for a variable period of time. In our case, given the current state of research on PMFCs and with the loads currently connected, we can use the sensor for approximately 30-40 minutes. In this period of time, the supercapacitor goes from an initial charge of 3000mV to one of 2500mV, i.e. 500mV. These 500mV will then be recharged by the PMFC in about 30 minutes (if the PMFC is performing well). The entire charge of the supercapacitor is used because otherwise it would take too long to recharge, leaving a gap in the data that is too long. It is therefore preferable to have intermittent data for short periods, which allow for the reconstruction of almost complete data, rather than having continuous data for a few hours, which would require an equally long recharge time, without being able to collect any information at this stage. The MyAmbience app also offers the ability to view data in real time, even remotely (by Bluetooth Low Energy). This feature is very useful where operators are forced to work in hazardous and/or electrically hazardous environments, as it allows them to view data from a safe distance, even through walls or glass.

Pulsed Light Generation

To let the operators know when sensor data is available in real time, a method was devised that could draw their attention. A very low-power LED circuit driver was therefore developed that, in addition to drawing attention, also serves a utilitarian and aesthetic purpose by illuminating dark spaces that are difficult to reach from the electrical network. To save even more energy, these LEDs are not always on, but flash, thus attracting even more attention. To do this, we used a circuit called a "Duty Regulator" based on logic gates (NAND, NOT), which allow the flashing frequency to be varied depending on which branch of the two circuits exploiting diodes is conducting (through different resistors value) (Figure. 14).

Figure 14 – Schematic of the developed LED duty regulator circuit (pulsed)

Recalling the principle that determines the circuit's time constant in digital gates transitions and delays, $\tau = R \cdot C \cdot \ln(2)$, it is possible to see how, given the same capacitance, it is possible to vary the on/off time by raising or lowering the resistors R_1 and R_2 in the two branches. This gives: $\tau_1 = R_1 \cdot C$ and $\tau_2 = R_2 \cdot C$. To obtain the desired duty cycle, the resistors will be sized appropriately, obtaining $\tau_1 \ll \tau_2$ considering τ_1 as on and τ_2 as off. On each of these branches there is a diode, to prevent current from flowing into the branch where it shouldn't, otherwise it would invalidate all the considerations made regarding the choice of resistors. By sizing these resistors, it is possible to choose the flashing duty cycle, which in our case will be asymmetrical. Considering energy savings, an asymmetrical duty cycle of 10% was chosen (Figure 15). This light fraction appears much larger to the human eye, giving the effect of a 40% duty cycle, thus achieving a significant energy saving without losing effectiveness.

Figure 15 – Fabricated Duty Regulator for pulsed LEDs

The Smart Jar Prototype

A smart Jar prototype has been developed in cooperation with Sketch-In third party company and its subcontractor 2lam design team. The Jar includes: PMFC generator with water level regulation, a real plant with saucer to maximize bacteria community presence, a DC-DC boost for energy harvesting, a wireless temperature and humidity sensor and a pulsed array of diodes. The developed prototype is reported in its details Figure 16 (a, b, c, d). Electronics and PMFC are in separate volumes in order to avoid circuit contamination with conductive (mineralized) water.

Figure 16a - The developed smart jar (full view)

Figure 16b - The developed smart jar (detail of pulsed light)

Figure 16c - The developed smart jar (detail of percolating water onto PMFC section)

Figure 16d - The developed smart jar (Breakdown)

PMFC Actual Continuous Available Power (Bacteria's Power)

Final measurements of current and voltage were taken using a high performance PMFC sample in order to know the power available from a good PMFC element calculated in terms of figure of merit (FoM) (in Watt) as $FoM = f_{em} \cdot I_{short} / 4$. As reported below, the values are strongly different, as expected with and without a plant over the cell. With the plant, the power available is higher because of higher bacterial community proliferation. This data, which should be taken as an empowerment of the preliminary reported results, is still related to peak power obtainable from the PMFC (Table 8) and cannot be delivered for an indetermined amount of time.

Table 8 -Final measurement on high performance PMFC sample (peak power FoM value)

	Current (mA)	Voltage (mV)	FoM(uW)
With plant	1.568	972	381
Without plant	1.230	843	259

However, the most interesting measure during the project terminal part has been the evaluation of the continuous available power from a PMFC element, which is actually the power obtained thanks to the current instantly generated by the bacteria community without considering charge accumulation effects in the soil or other artificial tanks. In order to measure this quantity, a variable load has been employed. The PMFC was connected to a variable resistor (max value of

100 k Ω) and measurements of voltage and peak current were taken from 50.0 k Ω down to 15.0 k Ω , with 5.0 k Ω stepping. On the other hand, in the range from 15.0 k Ω down to 10.0 k Ω the step intervals were of 0.5 k Ω . The turning point can be found by evaluating (over long-time measures) the minimum load value for which the current (maximum, being the load minimum) remains stable for different hours (up to 1 day) instead of just few minutes (like in the extended peak power experiments). This turning point, even for different PMFCs samples, was always in the order of 10 k Ω load value. When the resistance decreases more than such optimal value, the current is not stable anymore over long times. While the cell is connected to the load around 10 k Ω (or more), the current was constantly available, without decreasing for even 24 hours (Table 9).

Table 9 – Final measurements of actual available continuous power from a high performance PMFC (bacteria's current)

R_{LOAD}=10.5 kΩ	Current (μA)	Voltage(mV)	Power (μW)
With plant	93	510	47.3
Without plant	80	430	34.4

Finally, the PMFC was connected to a more complex load, made of a DC-DC boost converter with a super-capacitor accumulator followed by a thermometer and a pulsed led array. The PMFC can give enough energy to make the system work for usually around 15 min (up to 45 minutes with sensor only). The peak power FoM evaluation can be used for a fast estimation of the actual continuous available power, since laboratory measurements demonstrated that the two factors always differ by about an order of magnitude. As rule of thumb is thus enough to divide the FoM by a factor of 10 to 20 depending on the PMFC type and performance to have an idea of the bacteria's instant current. An estimation of the order of magnitude is in fact sufficient for considering the possible exploitation of the generator.